

Lightelligence

Second prototype report

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Introduction:

This report explains the hardware and software implemented on the second Lightelligence prototype.

The main objective of this project is to obtain a light spectrum and reproduce it driving several LED's channels with different wave lengths.

This second approach uses MatLab and Android programs to process the spectrum, obtaining certain parameters, for example xy or uv coordinates, color temperature, CRI or power efficiency, which will be processed to obtain the best working value for each LED channel.

This report is divided as follows:

- Hardware
 - Driver board.
 - LED's board.
 - Hamamatsu mini-spectrometer C10988MA
 - Linear technologies LT8500 PWM generator
 - STM32F100 discovery board
 - ARF32 Bluetooth module
- Software
 - Configuration
 - Main program
 - Acquiring spectrum
 - Sending UART data
 - Receiving UART data
 - Sending SPI data

Hardware

This chapter focuses on the principal elements, configurations and connections of the prototype.

Figure 1 shows a picture of the Lightelligence second prototype (without reflector). It shows the light engine, the Hamamatsu spectrometer over the power supply and the box which contains the driver board.

Figure 1: Lightelligence second prototype.

Hardware components:

- 24V-4.8A power supply, which provides the main power to the system.
- The STM32F100RBT6B microprocessor implemented inside the ST discovery evaluation board.
- LT8500 PWM generator.
- ARF32 Bluetooth module.
- LED drivers based on National Semiconductor LM3406 chip.
- Hamamatsu C10988MA mini-spectrometer.
- Philips Lumileds Rebel LEDs (12 different wavelengths).
- Microchip MCP98242 temperature sensor

In the follow subsections each component will be explained.

Driver Board

Figure 2 shows the driver board where the different components and connectors can be seen:

Figure 2: Both sides of the driver board.

The components and connectors of the driver board can be located by the numbers as follow:

1. Connectors for the STM32 Discovery evaluation board.
2. GAIN selector. Here a LOW or HIGH gain for the Hamamatsu spectrometer can be selected.
3. Hamamatsu connector.
4. Communications connector.
5. 5V voltage regulator.
6. Voltage communicator selector. There are 3 options:
 - a. USB selected: this option is in case that the connections are done with the FTDI USB to serial cable that supplies 5V to the microcontroller. It is also necessary to leave selectors 7 and 9 in BT mode.
 - b. BT selected: this option is in case that the Bluetooth module is used. It will supply 3.3V to the module.
 - c. No jumper: this option is in case that 5V is supplied for the STM32 Discovery evaluation board interface when the STM32F100RBT6B is programmed. It is also necessary to leave selectors 7 and 9 in BT mode.

7. Microcontroller supply selector. There are 2 options:
 - a. USB selected: 5V is supplied by the communications cable or by the programming interface.
 - b. BT selected: 5V is supplied by the on board 5V regulator.
8. 24V main connector to supply power to the drivers and eventually to the microcontroller.
9. 5V regulator selector. There are 2 options:
 - a. USB selected: 5V is supplied by the communications cable or by the programming interface leaving the 5V regulator disconnected.
 - b. BT selected: The 5V regulator is connected to the 24V supply, generating the microcontroller supply voltage.
10. PWM generator LT8500.
11. LED board connectors.
12. The 13 channel drivers.

LED Board

Hamamatsu mini-spectrometer C10988MA

This spectrometer has an analog serial output which is represented 256 different wave lengths, from 340nm to 750nm (1.6 nm step).

Figure 1 shows the Hamamatsu C10988MA pinout :

Pin No.	Symbol	Name of pin	I/O	Description
1	CLK	Clock pulse	I	Sensor scan sync signal
2	GND	Ground		GND
3	NC			No connection
4	ST	Start pulse	I	Start pulse
5	NC			No connection
6	Gain	Gain	I	Image sensor: gain setting
7	EOS	End of scan	O	EOS (end of scan) signal
8	NC			No connection
9	Vdd	Supply voltage	I	Power supply of image sensor: 5 V
10	Video	Video output	O	Video output signal

Figure 3: Hamamatsu C10988MA pinout.

For the Hamamatsu C10988MA connection it has been used the Hamamatsu C11351-02 board, which allows the easy and not soldering electrical connection of the Hamamatsu C10988MA pins into a commercial connector. It also provides also an output buffer for the Video output signal using the OPA 350 UA. Figure 2 shows the Hamamatsu C11351-02 board:

Figure 4: Hamamatsu C11351-02 board.

The first image is where the Hamamatsu C10988MA pins are plugged in, the second image shows the OPA 350 UA configured as a buffer (sometimes it blows and has to be replaced). It is also shown the 10 pins commercial connector where all system is easily plugged. The original connector has been changed in order to make easy connections between components.

The 10 pins connector pinout is described in the next table:

Pin connector number	Corresponding to Hamamatsu pin	Corresponding to signal name	Corresponding to STM32F100
1	1	CLK	PB0
2	2	GND	GND
3	4	ST	PB1
4	6	GAIN	5V or GND
5	7	EOS	PD2
6	2	GND	GND
7	9	VDD	5V
8	2	GND	GND
9	-	Buffered video	PC0
10	2	GND	GND

The working mode is carried out by two input signals, CLK and ST. CLK is the clock needed to shift the 256 registers and the ST is the start of transmission signal and also control de exposure time, which is the period between two ST signals. To start one spectrum transmission the ST signal has to be low during the falling edge of the CLK signal. Then start the steps of 4 clocks, before start a new step and during the last clock pulse, the C10988MA gives the output by the video signal, as shown figure 3:

Figure 5: Timing chart signals (Left) and the corresponding measured signals (Right).

When the C10988MA output video buffer is finish after 256 steps, the EOS (end of sequence) is lowered during 4 clocks, a new measurement can be started after the EOS signal rising edge.

Figure 6: Timing chart signals (Left) and measured signals of a real spectrum (Right) (day light and fluorescence).

Texas instruments TLC5940

The TLC5940 is a 16-channel, constant-current sink LED driver. Each channel has an individually adjustable 4096-step grayscale PWM brightness control and a 64-step, constant-current sink (dot correction). The dot correction adjusts the brightness variations between LED channels and other LED. The dot correction data is stored in an integrated EEPROM. Both grayscale control and dot correction are accessible via a serial interface. A single external resistor sets the maximum current value of all 16 channels.

Using the TLC5940 have been tried the spectrum reproduction, which have been obtained for the Hamamatsu C10988MA. The figure 5 shows the LED's and TLC5940 mounted in a PCB board:

Figure 7: First prototype Lightelligence PCB bottom and top.

The TLC5940 needs to be controlled by the signals GSCLK, BLANK, SCLK, SIN and XLAT. The grayscale PWM cycle starts with the falling edge of BLANK. The first GSCLK pulse after BLANK goes low increases the grayscale counter by one and switches on all 16 OUTs. Meaning every 4096 pulses on GSCLK, the grayscale counter has to be reset by a BLANK pulse. The value of each 16 OUTs PWM can be managed by the SPI bus, sending a 192 bits frame (16 x 12bits). This frame is sent by the controller using the SCLK and SIN pins and the data is stored into a 192 bits shift register, once all data is transferred, one XLAT rising edge latch the data into a grayscale register. The value of each channel have to be 0 to 4095, the output is high while the channel value is higher than the grayscale counter, once the channel value is equal to the grayscale value, the output becomes low, switching off the LED of these channel. Figure 6 shows the timing chart:

Figure 8: Grayscale PWM cycle timing chart.

Figure 7 shows the 192 bits transmission timing chart:

Figure 9: 192 bits transmission timing chart.

The cable name and color is described in the next table:

Signal name	Corresponding to STM32F100	Corresponding color
VCC	3.3V	Red
GND	-	Black
GSCLK	PC7	White
XLAT	PA4	Yellow
BLANK	PB7	Red
SCLK	PA5	Green
SIN	PA7	Blue
DC PROG	-	Blue
V PROG	-	Yellow

The cable name and the position in the connector are described in the next draw:

STM32F100 discovery board

The STM32 value line Discovery evaluation board is designed to discover the STM32 microprocessors and help to develop and share the applications. It is based on an STM32F100RB and includes ST-Link embedded debug tool interface, LEDs and push buttons.

Figure 8 shows the STM32F100 discovery board:

Figure 10: STM32F100 discovery board.

In the software chapters will be explained deeply the microprocessor and the signal construction, in this chapter it is shown the electrical connections. Next table put together all the microprocessor pins used to manage all the components:

STM32F100RB Ports	Pin Mode	Hamamatsu	TLC 5940	PC
PB0	Output	CLK		
PB1	Output	ST		
PC0	Input	VIDEO		
PD2	Input	EOS		
PA4	Output		XLAT	
PA5	Output		SCLK	
PA7	Output		SIN	
PB7	Output		BLANK	
PC7	Output		GSCLK	
PC10	Output			Tx (Yellow)
PC11	Input			Rx (Red)

Software

This chapter is focused on the STM32F100RB program used to control all peripherals devices, it is also explained the ports configuration to manage all the signals needed.

Configuration

The STM32F100xx value line family incorporates the high-performance ARM Cortex™-M3 32-bit RISC core operating at a 24 MHz frequency, high-speed embedded memories (Flash memory up to 128 Kbytes and SRAM up to 8 Kbytes), and an extensive range of enhanced peripherals and I/Os connected to two APB buses. All devices offer standard communication interfaces (up to two I2Cs, two SPIs, one HDMI CEC, and up to three USARTs), one 12-bit ADC, two 12-bit DACs, up to six general-purpose 16-bit timers and an advanced-control PWM timer.

To manage all the signals in the microcontroller has been programmed some of the alternative functions that can be selected on the ports, next table shows which functions, at which pin ports have been selected and which are the content files:

Alternative function	Port pin and name	Signal name	File configuration
ADC1	PC0 - ADC1_IN10	VIDEO	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
SPI1	PA5 - SPI1_SCK	SCKL	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
SPI1	PA7 - SPI1_MOSI	SIN	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
USART3	PC10 - USART3_TX	Tx	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
USART3	PC11 - USART3_RX	Rx	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
TIMER1	PB0 - TIM1_CH2N	CLK	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
TIMER4	PB7 - TIM3_CH2	BLANK	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
TIMER3	PC7 - TIM4_CH2	GSCLK	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
GPIOB	PB1 - OUTPUT	ST	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
GPIOA	PA4 - OUTPUT	XLAT	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c
EXTI	PD2 – External Int	EOS	hamamatsu.h hamamatsu.c

Main program

The main program is based on a infinite loop, it starts waiting a user bottom interruption (press bottom) and always do the same, acquire a spectrum from Hamamatsu C10988MA, send this data by the UART, if it is ready receive data from the UART and finally send data to the TLC5940 by the SPI bus. Next flux diagram show the main program flux:

First step consist in configure all ports as a desired function.

Once configured, the program waits until user bottom press to start.

Once started, the microcontroller starts to acquire the spectrum 256 points from Hamamatsu C10988MA.

Here is also programmed a wait time to control the espoused time, after this time each acquired spectrum is sent by the UART to a serial interface.

The computer shall change the LED's PWM data depending on the spectrum received, it is not time scheduled, so the answer will be sent once the fixing algorithm finish. The LED's PWM will not change until receive all the data, it will happen when the received data bit is set, then the SPI buffer is saved with the new data.

It is also set the espoused time of the Hamamatsu C10988MA.

Figure 9 shows the main program without waiting time, so with the minimum espoused time:

Figure 11: Main results without waiting time oscilloscope view.

Acquiring spectrum

As shown in figure 3, Hamamatsu C10988MA needs the ST signal low in a falling edge of the CLK signal to start the spectrum acquisition. The spectrum is given using 256 different positions or wave lengths, which are separated each one for 4 clocks.

The function in charge of manage these signals is `void Enable_Line (FunctionalState Start_Step, FunctionalState Take_Data)`, where the variables `Start_Step` and `Take_Data` can be selected as ENABLE or DISABLE. Enabling `Start_Step` is generated the ST signal low to start the spectrum acquisition, disabling `Start_Step` the ST signal remain always high. The variable `Take_Data` is thought to enable or disable the acquisition, in this case the variable is always enabled.

This function is divided in 8 states, which allow us to manage the 4 periods of the clock signal (`CLK`, `PB0`), assuming one phase high and another low in each period. Next flux diagram show the acquiring spectrum flux and state machine:

Some of the states presented above have more functions than the wait one, following are described all the functionalities:

First_Step = if Start_Step is enabled, the *ST* signal (PB1) is lowered at the beginning of the state, using the next code: *GPIO_ResetBits (GPIOB, GPIO_Pin_1)*; To leave this state into the Second_Step state is needed a *CLK* change to low.

Second_Step = if Start_Step is enabled, the *ST* signal (PB1) is raised leaving the state into the Third_Step state with a *CLK* change to high, using the next code: *GPIO_SetBits (GPIOB, GPIO_Pin_1)*;

Third_Step = waiting state. To leave this state into the Fourth_Step state is needed a *CLK* change to low.

Fourth_Step = waiting state. To leave this state into the Fifth_Step state is needed a *CLK* change to high.

Fifth_Step = if *Take_Data* is enabled, the 12 bits ADC1 is switched on the first time leaving the state into the Sixth_Step state with a *CLK* change to low.

Sixth_Step = if *Take_Data* is enabled, the ADC1 is switched on the second time and wait for the measurement finish. To leave this state into the Seventh_Step state is needed a *CLK* change to high.

Seventh_Step = if *Take_Data* is enabled, the data of the ADC1 is saved into the *Landa* variable leaving the state into the Eighth_Step state with a *CLK* change to low. *Landa* is a 256x16 bits unsigned integer array and the variable *Position* is in charge to point where save inside the array.

Eighth_Step = this is the last state and where the *Enable_Line* decides if exit or return to the first state. First of all the state waits a *CLK* change to high. Once *CLK* change, it is checked if *Start_Step* is enabled and if the variable *Position* has finished covering the entire *Landa* array, which is done overflowing the variable (the *Position* variable is defined as 8 bits unsigned integer, just to point to 256 positions, incrementing *Position* when the value is 256 will result 0). If any of these two conditions is true, it is changed the value of the variable *Exit* to DISABLE, which is the condition to leave *Enable_Line*. If the conditions are false, the program will jump into the First_Step state.

There are some signal that have been configured before, these signals are:

CLK, Timer1 has been configured as a $12 \text{ MHz} / 127 = 92 \text{ KHz}$ output clock in PWM 50% mode, this signal is driven by the PBO port. It is needed to increase the clock time, it shall to be changed by modifying the *CCR1_Val* variable, the reset value is $0x7F = 127$.

ADC1, it is a 12 bits ADC configured as a single shoot, this configuration needs to wake up the ADC before measure, and it is done in the Fifth_Step. The sample time is configured at 13 clock cycles and the input port is PC0.

And the *ST* and *EOS* signal are output and input with external interrupt respectively. *ST* is configured at PBO and *EOS* is at PD2.

Sending UART data

This function is in charge of send the spectrum to a computer that will process it and will return the value to be sent to each LED channel, the communications will be done using the UART (Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter).

The sending UART data is done by the function `HAMAMATSU_USART_Send_data ()`; as the UART sends only 8 bits at the same time, and as the *Landa* data array is 12 bits each position, it shall to be divided in two separated bytes per position. This separation is done by the function `void Send_Two_Bytes(USART_TypeDef* USARTx, uint16_t Data)` where `USARTx` is the used USART, in this case it is the `HAMAMATSU_USART`, defined as `USART3` and the `uint16_t Data` is the 16 bits data to be separated into a 2 x 8 bits.

Apart of the data it is also send the data position into the *Landa* array, and finally a control byte, so the frame sent is composed as follows:

Position byte + High data byte + Low data byte + control byte (0x0D)

It is send 256 times, until finish the entire *Landa* array. So the program sends 4 x 256 bytes = 1KB each spectrum.

Next diagram flow shows the flux to send UART data:

Receiving UART data

This function is in charge to receive the computer data, which will be sent once the spectrum is processed. This data reception is managed by an interruption, each data received has 8 bits length and it is stored in the *Tempo* variable, which is a 36 x 8 bits unsigned integer array and it is divided in 16 x 2 LED PWM data (12 bits each = 2 x data received) and 4 x 8 bits that will change the value of the 32 bits unsigned integer variable *Wait_Time* that control the Hamamatsu C10988MA exposure time.

Next diagram flow shows the flux to receive UART data:

The UART is configured as is indicate at the next table:

Baud rate	230400
Data length	8 bits
Parity	None
Stop bits	1
Hardware flow control	No

Sending SPI data

With this function the microcontroller communicates with the TLC5940, which control the 16 PWM LED channels. As explained before, each PWM channel is controlled by changing the value of a 12 bits register. So, it has to be sent $16 \times 12 = 192$ bits by the SPI bus.

The main problem is that the SPI sends 8 bits each time, and the PWM data is 12 bits. To solve this problem has been used the shift register option. The TLC5940 PWM channel LED data frame is shown in figure 10:

Figure 12: TLC5940 PWM channel LED data frame.

This data frame is Big-endian format, which means that the most significant bit (MSB) of the last channel is sent first. To build this frame has been needed to use three times the SPI to send two channels: (for this example it is supposed 15th channel = 0x0XYZ and 14th = 0x0RTS and each letter represents 4 bits)

First sending are the 12 to 5 bits of the 15th channel, to do that it is needed to shift 4 times right the 15th channel using a 16 bits variable (Calculo): $0x0XYZ \gg 4 = 0x00XY$.

Second sending are the 4 to 1 bits of the 15th channel and the 12 to 9 bits of the 14th channel, it is needed to shift left 12 times the 15th channel and add the result to the 14th channel value, then the result has to be shifted right 8 times: $0x0XYZ \ll 12 = 0xZ000$; $0xZ000 + 0x0RTS = 0xZRTS$; $0xZRTS \gg 8 = 0x00ZR$.

Third sending are the 8 to 1 bits of the 14th channel: $0x0RTS = 0x00TS$.

So the first 24 frame bits are: 0xXYZRTS, corresponding to 15th and 14th channels. The method is used for the rest of the channels.

Next diagram flow shows the flux to send SPI data:

The configuration of the ports to manage all the signals involved in the TLC5940 control is as follows:

The GSCLK signal is generated by the channel 2 of the Timer3, using the toggle mode and a CCR2 value of 0x04, obtaining a 1.333MHZ signal. It is used the PC7 as alternative out pin.

The BLANK signal is obtained by the channel 2 of the Timer4, using the PWM mode, a CCR2 value of 0x5FF0, a period value of 0x5FFF and a prescaler value of 0x02. It is used the PB7 as alternative out pin.

The SPI is configured as follows:

Direction	2 Lines Full Duplex
Mode	Master
Data size	8 bits
Baud rate	Prescaler 256
First bit	MSB

The SPI used is the SPI1 and the pins are PA5 for the SCLK and PA7 for the SIN (MOSI), both configured as alternative output.

And the XLAT signal is configured at the PA4 as output. It is raised when the SPI has sent all the data channels and the BLANK signal is high. It is lowered before the BLANK signal drops to low.